

SCHOOL FEEDING PROGRAMME AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS, AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

School Feeding Programme constitute a critical intervention that has been introduced in many developed and developing countries of the world to address the issue of poverty, stimulate school enrolment and enhance pupils' academic performance. The study adopted survey research design. The objective of this study was to ascertain the relationship between school feeding programme and pupils' class test performance, retention and completion rate. Research objectives was set, hypothesis formulated to guide the research and the survey design was employed. Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs and Expectancy theory was adopted as its theoretical framework Its main tool for inquiries was a researcher-developed instrument tagged 'Home-Grown School Feeding and Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools. The target population of the study comprised public primary school teachers and head teachers in Akwa Ibom State, totaling 235,215. The stratified sampling technique was used to select public primary school teachers from three local government areas- Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene, to form the sample. Simple linear regression model of ANOVA was used to test and interpret the hypotheses with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and class test performance and retention in public primary schools, but without a corresponding increase in completion rate and academic performance. The study recommends among others that government should ensure that foods rich in iodine, zinc and iron are provided to pupils to enhance the brain function for optimal academic performance.

KEYWORDS: School Feeding Programme, Academic performance, Class performance, Retention. Completion.

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement which is synonymous to academic performance, refers to the extent to which students have achieved mastery of the subjects they are exposed to in the schools. According to Ward et al (2006), academic performance refers to the outcome of education; the extent to which the students, teachers or institutions, have achieved their educational goals. Academic performance refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies.

There are many factors that contribute to academic performance, one of them is proper nutrition. Nutrition plays a role in academic performance. Poor nutrition can leave students susceptible to illness or lead to headaches and stomachaches, resulting in school absences (Brown et al, 2008). Access to nutrition that incorporates protein, carbohydrates, and glucose has been shown to improve students' cognition, concentration, and energy levels (Graham 2010). According to him, school feeding contributes to the education and well-being of children. A hungry child does not grow well, cannot learn and faces many health risks in the future. School Feeding Programme is an organized programme that alleviates hunger while supporting education, health and community development (WFP, 2007).

All over the world, social safety nets are tools government use to help vulnerable people tackle hunger and poverty. In Nigeria, successive governments have expressed concern about the country's high poverty level despite being endowed with enormous resources. Programmes such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Green Revolution, otherwise known as "Back to Land," Directorate for Food, Roads, and Infrastructure (DFRI), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Better Life Programme, Peoples Bank Project, Family Support Programme, National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), and National Poverty Eradication Programme (NPEP), have been initiated at different times to tackle the high level of poverty in the country (Mboho, 2022).

In 2016, the Buhari administration established the National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) to combat poverty and hunger nationwide. The components of the administration's Social Investment Programme include the N-Power Programme, the National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP), the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programme, and the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP), which consists of the Market-Moni, Farmer-Moni, and Trader-Moni schemes. The suite of programmes under the NSIP focuses on ensuring a more equitable distribution of resources to vulnerable populations, including children, youth and women. Since 2016, these programmes combined have supported more than 4 million beneficiaries country-wide through a fair and transparent process supported by the Ministry of Budget and National Planning (MBNP) and other notable Ministries, Department and Agencies with aligned goals.

The N-power programme is designed to assist young Nigerians between the ages of 18 to 35 to acquire and develop life-long skills for becoming change makers in their communities and players in the domestic and global markets and given a stipend of ₦30,000 monthly. The Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programme directly supports those within the lowest poverty bracket by improving nutrition, increasing household consumption and supporting the development of human capital through cash benefits to various categories of the poor and vulnerable. The support is conditioned on fulfilling soft and hard co-responsibilities that enable recipients improve their standard of living. Government Enterprise and Empowerment

Programme (GEEP) is a micro-lending intervention that targets traders, artisans, enterprising youth, farmers and women in particular, by providing loans between 10,000 and 100,000 at no monthly cost to beneficiaries. The Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSP) aims to deliver school feeding to young children with a specific focus on increasing school enrollment, reducing the incidence of malnutrition (especially among the poor and those ordinarily unable to eat a meal-a-day), empowering community women as cooks and by supporting small farmers that help stimulate economic growth.

The introduction of school feeding is traced to the Millennium Development Goals (MDG's) initiative introduced in many developed and developing countries. School feeding programs are interventions that regularly provide nutritious foods to children and adolescents attending school. Benefits of school feeding on children and adolescents include alleviating hunger, reducing micronutrient deficiency and anemia, preventing overweight and obesity, improving school enrollment and attendance, increasing cognitive and academic performance, and contributing to gender equity in access to education (WFP, 2007).

In developing countries, almost 60 million children go to school hungry every day and about 40 percent of them are from Africa. Providing school meals is therefore vital in nourishing children. Parents are motivated to send their children to school instead of keeping them at home to work or care for siblings (Akanbi, 2013). As a result, the Federal Government came up with the Universal Basic Education Act in 2004, which provided the enabling legislative backing for the execution of the Home-Grown School Feeding Programme.

The majority of the estimated 7.3 million children out of school in Nigeria are girls. In 2005, the Federal Government of Nigeria launched the School Feeding Programme with the assistance of the United Nations' Children Education Fund (UNICEF) and the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD). Since then, the enrolment rate had increased while the attendance of pupils in school is stable especially among girls who used to leave school for street trading and house-help jobs. (WFP, 2007). Food benefits given to pupils such as school meals make up for additional childcare expenses for parents. School feeding goes far beyond the plate of food, producing high returns in the following critical areas: education and gender equality, health and nutrition; social protection and local economies and agriculture. These include the perceived value of education, the availability of job opportunities, schools' direct and indirect costs, and the availability and quality of school facilities (Mboho, 2022).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria, poor nutritional habit is usually attributable to poverty, lack of information on good diet and negligence on the part of food handlers and parents. Poor nutrition has also been shown to be an underlying cause for poor attendance, retention and achievement in education among children of school age. Malnourished children do not concentrate on their studies, have problem of low retention, and low or epileptic attendance. Due to economic recessions that is affecting many people in Nigeria, some parents find it difficult to provide adequate diet for their children and this affects their academic performance. The number of students enrolled in public primary schools that enjoy free meals are increasing every day because some parents prefer to enroll their children in schools benefiting from the programme.

Education in Akwa Ibom state remains top priority for the government, and several efforts have been made to carry out meaningful reforms in the sector. There have been major reforms by the state government towards improvement of education quality in the state.

Although grounded on the National Policy on Education, Akwa Ibom State's Education Policy is also informed by national and international agreements' policies and targets. At the international level, such policies are the Sustainable Development Goals and Education. At the national and state levels, the policy documents include the Education Sector Plan, Economic Recovery and Growth Plan, Gender Policy, Annual School Census Report, Annual Education Sector Performance Report, UBE Act, and National Education Roadmap (Mboho, 2023). The central objective of the School Feeding programme is to improve academic performance of primary school pupils in Nigeria by addressing the problem of poor nutrition and health status of children who have been affected as a result of poverty, which has affected the learning outcomes of the children (NHGSFP, 2017).

The Federal Government has spent 4.5 billion naira in 2016/17 and 6 billion naira in 2017/18 on school feeding in 14 States. From this feeding programme, over 6 million primary school pupils were fed and about 33,000 cooks were employed and paid. From this amount, Akwa Ibom State received a total sum of ₦119, 826,700 with which 623,558 pupils have been fed. A total of 5383 cooks were employed in 899 schools under the programme in the State (The mail newspaper, June 7, 2021). As at June 2021, Akwa Ibom state received 15 tranche payments amounting to ₦ 4,815,194,300.00. Again, the State Annual School Census report (2019) showed a continued increase in pupils' enrolment and attendance in the participating schools. (Jumare, 2020).

In spite the implementation of the School Feeding Programme, statistics revealed that Akwa Ibom state ranks second highest in Nigeria and highest among the southern states with 581,800 estimated number of out of school children at primary school level in 2017/2018. This data was earlier published in the 2018 digest of basic education statistics by the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC). In terms of gender population of out of school children, Akwa Ibom had the largest with 298,161. (Premium Times Newspaper 8 Sept., 2021, Mboho, 2022).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The **General objective** of the study is to examine School Feeding Programmes and academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

The **Specific objectives** are:

- i. to examine the relationship between School Feeding Programme and Class test performance of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. to determine the relationship between School Feeding Programme and Retention of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. to ascertain the relationship between School Feeding Programme and Completion rate of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypotheses was tested in this study at 0.05 alpha level of significance to ascertain its level of acceptance or otherwise.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and Class test performance of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and Retention of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and Completion rate of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

School Feeding Programme and Academic Performance

School feeding helps to alleviate short-term hunger in pupils. The WFP (2004) reported that the effects of short-term hunger related to learning capacity in which learning ability is affected greatly by hunger due to skipped meals. The provision of a School Feeding Programme, for example, a small snack at the start of the day or mid-morning alleviates short-term hunger and has been linked to increased awareness, activeness and improved learning capacity (Briggs, 2008).

It has also been noted that school feeding aids in the improvement of nutritional status in learners. The school feeding programme helps to improve the nutritional status as well as the health status of school children, as they learn better if they are not hungry. The poorly fed school children who are provided with good meals improve their growth and school performance, and prevent anemia and other nutritional deficiencies (King and Burgess, 1995; Mboho, 2022).

School Feeding and Class Performance

Academic achievement and performance, as well as a child's learning process, can be hindered by poor and malnutrition. Academic achievement is the outcome or performance related to education that indicates the extent to which a child has accomplished a specific goal. A lasting consequence of malnutrition is impaired academic performance and poor academic scores (Prangthip et al, 2018). Nutritional and health status are powerful influences on a child's learning and how a child performs in school. Children who lack certain nutrients in their diet do not have the same potential for learning as healthy and nourished children. Children with cognitive and sensory impairments naturally perform less and are more likely to repeat grades. Malnutrition is oftentimes the result of food insecurity. Children who are food-insecure experience a smaller increase in reading and mathematics performances compared to children who do not lack access to nutritious foods (Cooper, 2019). Simply by having decreased access to nutritious foods, some elementary-aged students are automatically on course to have poorer academic achievement compared to their schoolmates who do not struggle to receive adequate nutrition.

Furthermore, poor nutrition in young children often means that the child is not eating enough of the foods that supply them with healthy vitamins and nutrients. These nutrients are not only vital for their physical and mental growth and development but also for having successful learning outcomes. Children with nutrient intake deficiencies have been linked with learning deficiencies, lower arithmetic grades, and the likelihood of having to repeat a grade (Basch, 2011). Naturally, having deficiencies in learning abilities will result in lower grades as grades are an assessment of academic performance. Being that the majority of schools focus on grades as a tool for assessing whether or not a student is prepared to advance to the next class, many students with learning deficiencies and poor grades are obligated to retake the same class level. A routine way to measure a student's level of academic achievement and performance in an area of learning is through grades, acquired by tests and test scores. Thus, grades are intended to reflect academic performance toward learning goals (Prangthip, 2018).

High grades and test scores represent a high level of academic achievement of a specific learning goal and low grades and test scores consequently represent the opposite. To examine the relationship between the intake of healthful versus less-healthful food group intake on academic achievement in urban schoolchildren, a study was done using standardized test scores to assess academic achievement. The study demonstrated that a greater intake of less healthful foods, such as sweet and salty snacks, was associated with lower standardized Mathematics and English language test scores, suggesting that nutrient-poor foods are correlated with lower academic achievement in this population (Bleiweiss-Sande, 2019). Additionally, the findings of the study found a positive relationship between vegetable consumption and verbal test scores.

A related study also found positive associations between consuming healthy diets in early life, diets rich in fresh fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, to higher intelligence quotients later in life (Bleiweiss-Sande, 2019). This shows that the benefits of healthful nutrition are not exclusively related to improving academic test scores but overall academic achievement throughout life through increased intelligence quotients.

School breakfast programs provide students with an opportunity to begin their day on a positive and relaxing note; some schools use the same time when breakfast is being fed to students as a time to allow students to socialize and enjoy themselves (Basch, 2011). This may include reading, being read to, or socializing with their friends. Children believed that eating breakfast made them more active and participative in school, contributing to their performance in school (Prangthip et al, 2019). Through greater activity and participation in school and thus performance, students will subsequently have improved test scores and overall academic achievement.

In a California study, a strong association has been found between the percentages of students who eat breakfast and schools with higher academic scores (Taras, 2005). As cognitive functioning is improved by consuming a nutritional breakfast, students were able to aim for better test scores. By implementing the school breakfast program and providing breakfast to students in the classroom, it can be guaranteed that each child will be given breakfast that provides them with the necessary nutrients that will foster their ability to successfully learn that day, and perform well on tests. According to Alaimo, Olson and Frongillo (2001), food-insufficient children have significantly lower arithmetic scores and are more likely to have repeated a grade, and difficulty getting along with other children. This demonstrates that negative academic and psychosocial outcomes are associated with food insufficiency.

School Feeding Programme and Retention

Good nutrition during childhood lays the foundation for a healthy individual at later years of life. School-aged children grow rapidly; hence, it is of necessity to make provision for the needed diet at this stage of development. Good nutrition is the first line of defense against numerous childhood diseases, which can leave indelible mark on a child for life. The preschool years (i.e., 1-5 years of age) is a time of rapid and dramatic postnatal brain development (i.e. neural plasticity), and of fundamental acquisition of cognitive development (i.e. working memory, attention and inhibitory control). Nutrition has been related to cognitive development and abilities. Cognitive abilities are demonstrated by academic performance in school children. Cognition represents a complex set of higher mental functions sub-served by the brain, and includes attention, memory, thinking, learning, and perception (Bhatnagar and

Taneja, 2001).

Children should be provided with food that will give an adequate amount of energy such as fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and proteins. Proteins help to build human cells and sources are animal liver, lean red meat, fish, chicken, turkey, seafood, cheese, milk and eggs and some products derived from soybeans, green beans, dairy foods, peanut butter, soya products, nuts, seeds, wheat and legumes. Erickson (2006) opines that fat makes up more than 60% of the brain and acts as a messenger in partial control of aspects such as mood. Foods rich in omega-3 fatty acids include purified fish oils, canola oil, walnut oil, walnuts, soybeans, soybean oil, and pumpkin seeds. Omega-3 fatty acids such as those found in salmon, kiwi fruit, and walnuts, provide many benefits in improving memory and learning, much of which occurs at the synapses.

Carbohydrates which are the most important source of energy for the body during childhood could be derived from sugars, starches and fiber. It provides energy to all tissues in the human body, especially the brain and red blood cells which normally utilize glucose as the fuel for cell activity. Carbohydrates from whole grains, milk products, fruits, vegetables and legumes increase the nutrition of children's diet. Vitamins are essential and vital in a proper diet for small children. Vitamin A is necessary for correct development of vision, to guarantee the integrity of epithelial tissue and development of tissue differentiation. The main sources of vitamin A are: liver, dairy products, eggs, fish, margarine, fruits and vegetables. Vitamins B help in the growth, sustenance and development of children. Vitamin C is essential for optimum functioning of the immune system. It contains antioxidant properties and plays a significant support role in the process of iron absorption. Vitamin D in fish, dairy products and iodine obtained from sea foods, dairy products, enriched grains and iodized salt plays an essential role in metabolizing muscle functioning, cell proliferation and maturation and correct functioning of the immune system. Vital nutrients for school-age children include calcium found in dairy products and dairy-free calcium-fortified beverages, iron in meats and iron-fortified grains. Minerals in diet are good for children, most especially iron, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, sodium, zinc and iodine. Manganese and magnesium are two minerals essential for brain functioning; sodium, potassium and calcium play a role in message transmission and the thinking process. Erickson (2006) opined that vitamins and minerals are important substances for the functioning of the brain. Most important are the vitamins A, C, E, and B complex vitamins.

School feeding positively impacts Cognitive development and Education. Existing research makes a convincing case that nutrition and health interventions will improve school performance (WHO, 1992). Good health and nutrition are needed for concentration, regular school attendance and optimum class performance (Levinger, 1996). Kleinman and Green (2002) carried out a research study on the implementation of a universal breakfast program on the academic performance of school-aged children and found that children who participated in the program have improved nutrition status. Those children with improved nutrition status experienced decreased hunger, reduced absenteeism, and increased math scores. Taras (2005) found that schools which had a breakfast program not only had lower tardiness and absentee rates, but positive effects on brain function and higher scholastic scores as well. Verbal fluency, arithmetic, attention tests, memory, creativity, endurance, and general cognitive functioning were found to be a result of eating nutritious food.

School Feeding Programme and Completion Rate

Improvements in nutrition make students healthier, hence, students are likely to have fewer absences, attend classes more frequently, are able to retain lessons learnt and perform excellently during tests and examinations. According to Rosso and Marek (1996), lack of food provision in schools leads to pupils' repetition and dropout. When children are provided with no or poor nutrition, their weakened condition reduces their learning capacity and forces them to end their school journey prematurely or stay out of schools. Therefore, effective learning participation is hindered (Mboho, 2022).

According to Rausch (2013), protein found in meat, fish, milk and cheese, among others, are used to create neurotransmitters as chemical messengers to the brain. Lack of this substance, known as protein energy malnutrition, leads to poor student participation. A well-nourished pupil will perform well academically, coupled with adequate learning materials and will complete his/her academic year on time.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study was guided by the motivation theory, propounded by Abraham Maslow (1971) based on Hierarchy of Needs. He defined a need as a physiological or psychological deficiency that a person feels the compulsion to satisfy. These needs arranged in hierarchical order, can create tensions that can influence person's work attitudes and behaviors.

Food is a basic need. A hungry child is likely to be physically, psychologically, and socio-emotionally unhealthy which will affect his/her academics. In this case, the child would not be inspired to attend school, study, or even retain what he or she is taught, let alone concentrate on stability or protection needs, having friends, or enjoying their play business, among other needs. The child's normal growth is stunted; this child may fail to attend school or concentrate on learning and therefore perform poorly. A hungry child finds it difficult to concentrate in class when the stomach starts to grumble for food and there is none to feed on. This impact negatively on the child's thinking capacity which is reflected in tasks assigned.

As Murungi (2012) points out, food improves learning in a big way because a hungry kid can't learn properly. This type of child is unhappy, weak, and unable to focus or retain information in school, and he or she is likely to perform poorly. Lack of basic needs, such as those described above, can cause a child to be absent from school, which can lead to the child dropping out.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is the survey design. It involves asking questions of a cross-section of the population under study (Mboho, 2015). The total population of the teachers under study is 235,215. Based on this population, using the Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination, the sample size is approximately 400. Multi-stage sampling technique was applied to the study as follows; random sampling was used to select different schools implementing School Feeding Programme; Purposive sampling was used to select head teachers and also during interview with local Education Officer. (LEO) The primary and secondary sources of data were used to elicit information for this study. The major instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The simple linear regression was used to analyze data. The three

hypotheses were tested using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 2.0) using 5% as our level of significance.

RESULTS

Testing of Hypotheses

Research Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: School Feeding Programme has no significant relationship with Class test performance of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom state.

Table1: Simple Regression Analysis of School Feeding Programme and Class test performance of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom state.

N=375

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.302 ^a	.091	.089	1.00758
a. Predictors:(Constant),school feeding programme and Class test performance				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.110	1	38.110	37.539	.000 ^b
	Residual	378.674	373	1.015		
	Total	416.784	374			
a. Dependent Variable: Class test performance						
b. Predictors:(Constant), school feeding programme						

Source: Field Data (2023), Significantat.05

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.922	.187		15.598	.000
	School feeding programme	.286	.047	.302	6.127	.000

The results from the table 1 above showed that the R-value is 0.302 while the R² is 91 percent. This indicates a high degree of correlation. The results also showed that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the significant value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between school feeding programme and Class test performance in public primary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and Retention rate of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

**Table2: Simple Regression Analysis of School Feeding Programme and Retention rate of public primary schools
N=375**

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.269 ^a	.072	.070	.96274
a. Predictors:(Constant), school feeding programme and Retention rate				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.879	1	26.879	29.000	.000 ^b
	Residual	345.719	373	.927		
	Total	372.597	374			
a. Dependent Variable: retention						
b. Predictors:(Constant),school feeding programme						

Source: Field Data(2023), Significant at .05

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.943	.179		16.447	.000
	School feeding programme	.240	.045	.269	5.385	.000

The results from table 2 above showed that the R – value 0.269 while the R² is 72 percent. This indicates a high degree of correlation. The results also showed that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the significant value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between school feeding programme and retention rate in public primary schools in Akwa IbomState.

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between School Feeding Programme and Completion rate of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom State.

**Table3: Simple Regression Analysis of School Feeding Programme and Completion rate of public primary schools
N=375**

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.278 ^a	.077	.075	.96657
a. Predictors:(Constant), school feeding programme and Completion rate				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29.121	1	29.121	31.170	.000 ^b
	Residual	348.479	373	.934		
	Total	377.600	374			
a. Dependent Variable: completion rate						
b. Predictors: (Constant), school feeding programme						

Source: Field Data (2023), Significant at .05

Coefficients.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.916	.180		16.230	.000
	School feeding programme	.250	.045	.278	5.583	.000

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The results from table 32 showed that the R – value 0.278 while the R² is 77 percent. This indicates a high degree of correlation. The results also showed that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the significant value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between school feeding programme and completion rate in public primary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the effect of school feeding programme on academic performance of pupils in public primary schools, Akwa Ibom state. Based on the results of the analysis, the study found out that:

1. School feeding programme has a significant effect on pupils' class test performance in Akwa Ibom state based on the results of questionnaire analyzed. Accordingly, data from terminal examinations records show that since the introduction of school feeding programme, the performance of pupils in class assessments have improved.
2. School feeding programme has a significant effect on pupils' retention in Akwa Ibom state. The results of the analysis reveal that the....
However, the findings from the interview conducted with the class teachers in the study area is in conformity with the results obtained above, that SFP has significantly increased the retentive abilities of pupils in public primary schools.
3. School feeding programme has no significant effect on pupils' completion in Akwa Ibom state. This implies that the study does not have enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The participants especially in the rural areas attributed the decline in completion rate to child labor practices to pupils in primary 4 and 5. During rainy season, some of the pupils are made to join their parents and guardians in the farms, thereby missing classes and sometimes, a term.

CONCLUSION

School feeding programme can thus be a powerful instrument for achieving many multi-sectorial benefits in education such as, increase enrolment, gender equality, food security, poverty reduction, nutrition and health, and agricultural development. The recent food, fuel, and financial crises have highlighted the importance of school feeding programme both as a social safety net for children living in poverty and food security, and as a tool for stimulating local agricultural production and economic opportunities in rural communities. As good as the policy may look, some states are yet to domesticate it or provide sufficient funding towards achieving it. A lot of challenges were also discovered during the implementation process ranging from poor funding, delay in release of funds and also diversion of the food items by administrators etc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are put forward based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. Class teachers should develop better teaching methods that will motivate pupils to learn and while using the appropriate measurement technique, administer tests regularly.
2. Government should ensure that foods rich in iodine, zinc and iron are provided to the pupils to enhance their brain development and functioning.
3. Parents who withdraw their wards without academic completion should be sanctioned according to the child rights law.

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